

MARKETING TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ORQALI SPORT TASHKILOTLARI FAOLIYATI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO`LLARI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola mamlakatimizda sport sohasida amalga oshirilayotgan islohatlar hamda jismoniy tarbiya va sport menejerlari sohasidagi mutaxassislarni tayyorlash sifatiga qo'yiladigan modellarga qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Jismoniy tarbiya, sport va turizm sohasi, "Jismoniy tarbiya va sport sohasida kadrlarni tayyorlash hamda ilmiy tadqiqotlar tizimini yanada takomillashtirish choratadbirlari to'g'risida"gi qarori.

WAYS TO INCREASE THE EFFICIENCY OF SPORTS ORGANIZATIONS BY IMPROVING THE MARKETING SYSTEM

Abstract. This article focuses on the reforms implemented in the field of sports in our country and the models for the quality of training of specialists in the field of physical education and sports managers.

Keywords: physical education, sports and tourism, the decision "On measures to further improve the system of training and scientific research in the field of physical education and sports".

ПУТИ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ СПОРТИВНЫХ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЙ ПУТЕМ СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЯ СИСТЕМЫ МАРКЕТИНГА

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются реформы, реализуемые в сфере спорта в нашей стране, и модели качества подготовки специалистов в области физического воспитания и спортивных менеджеров.

Ключевые слова: физическое воспитание, спорт и туризм, решение «О мерах по дальнейшему совершенствованию системы подготовки кадров и научных исследований в области физического воспитания и спорта».

Zamonaviy dunyoda sportga, sog'lom turmush tarziga, to'g'ri ovqatlanishga bo'lgan qiziqishni oshirish tendentsiyasi mavjud. Sport sohasi rivojlanishda to'xtamaydi, atrofida ma'lum bir ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, davlat muhitini yaratadi. Sport inshootlari jadal rivojlanmoqda, sport mahsulotlari va xizmatlarini ishlab chiqarish sanoati rivojlanmoqda, sport namoyishlari va bayramlar tobora ko'payib bormoqda, har joyda sport bilan bog'liq billboardlarda reklamalarni ko'rishingiz mumkin.

Sport aholiga, nafaqat professional sportchilarga, balki ko'plab odamlarning turmush tarziga kuchli ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Sport faoliyat doirasini kengaytirdi, yanada qulay va demokratik

bo'ldi. Yaqin-yaqingacha, sportchi sport maydonchalarida har doim o'tkazgan va mukofot olgan barcha hayotlarini sportga bag'ishlaganlar deb atashlari mumkin edi. Endi sport mavzusiga hech qanday aloqasi bo'lmagan har qanday kishi deyarli o'zini sportchi deb atashlari mumkin, bu faqat fitness klubiga tashrif buyurish yoki bog'da kechqurun mashq qilishmi. Zamonaviy sport nafaqat odamlarni tiklashning universal mexanizmi, balki insonni o'z-o'zini anglash usuli bo'lib, so'nggi yillarda sport zamonaviy inson qadriyatlarini tizimida yetakchi o'rinlardan birini egallaydi. Bunday mashhurlik bilan sport sohasida ishlaydigan kompaniyalar iste'molchilarga to'g'ri ta'sir ko'rsatish uchun marketing faoliyatiga yondashuvlarini qayta ko'rib chiqishlari kerak.

Shunday qilib, ish mavzusining dolzarbligi aholi o'rtasida sportning ommaviyligini oshirish, sport sohasida faoliyat yuritayotgan kompaniyalarning samarali marketing faoliyatining ahamiyatini oshirish bilan bog'liq.

Yangilik sport marketingi uchun nazariy asosning etishmasligi. Biroq, biz sport marketingi masalalarini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan Rossiyada nashr qilingan ma'lumotlarni, internet manbalari bilan birgalikda xorijiy ma'lumotlarni tahlil qildik.

Ushbu ishning maqsadi sport sohasidagi marketing faoliyatining o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini o'rganish, muayyan tashkilotning marketing amaliyotini tahlil qilish, aholi o'rtasida sportni targ'ib qilish, marketing faoliyatini takomillashtirish bo'yicha tavsiyalarni ishlab chiqish uchun bevosita va bilvosita xizmat ko'rsatishdir.

Ushbu maqsadga erishish uchun quyidagi vazifalar belgilandi:

- * sportni boshqarishda marketingning xususiyatlarini o'rganish;
- * sport xizmatlari bozorida iste'molchini tanlashning asosiy parametrlarini ko'rib chiqing;
- * sportda marketing faoliyatining xususiyatlarini tahlil qilish;
- * "Shirintoy" bolalar markazi misolida marketing faoliyatini tahlil qilish
- * sportni samarali joylashtirish va sport sohasida marketing kompleksini takomillashtirish orqali kompaniyaning marketing faoliyatini takomillashtirish bo'yicha tavsiyalar berish.

Tadqiqot ob'ekti "Shirintoy" bolalar markazi - "Shirintoy" bolalar markazining marketing faoliyati bo'lib xizmat qildi.

Taqdim etilgan mavzuni tahlil qilish va natijalarni talqin qilish uchun ushbu mavzuni o'rganishning turli usullari ishlatilgan. Sifatli tadqiqot o'tkazish uchun chuqur intervyu berish usuli tanlandi. O'tkazilgan chuqur suhbatning asosiy maqsadi sportning potentsial iste'molchilarini nima qiziqtirayotganini, tanlangan auditoriya uchun eng mos bo'lgan axborot xabarini bilish, shuningdek, sportda marketingning qo'llanilishi haqida o'z fikrlarini bilish edi.

Tadqiqot sport haqida batafsil va chuqur ma'lumot olish uchun turli yoshdagi shaxslarni qabul qildi. Asosiy respondentlar sifatida bolalar markazi rahbarlari, murabbiy va o'qituvchilar, shuningdek, "Shirintoy" bolalar markazida ishtirok etgan respondentlar so'zga chiqdilar. Sifatli tadqiqot respondentlari tomonidan berilgan javoblar asosida miqdoriy tadqiqotlar o'tkazish uchun so'rovnoma tuzildi.

Miqdoriy tadqiqotlar Internet so'rovnomasi usuli bilan amalga oshirildi. Ushbu vosita sifatida Google xizmati ishlatilgan shakllar, respondentlarning javoblari olingan va keyinchalik tahlil qilingan va talqin qilingan. Masalan, sport bilan shug'ullanadigan yoki ularni bajarish istagi va niyatiga ega bo'lgan respondentlar tanlangan. Sport bilan shug'ullanishga to'sqinlik qiladigan

va bu qiziqishlarga ega bo'lmagan sog'liqni saqlash muammolari bo'lgan respondentlar chiqarib tashlandi.

Shuningdek, statistika ma'lumotlari, nashrlar, xorijiy va mahalliy tadqiqot, kon - salting kompaniyalari hisobotlari va axborot-tahlil portallari yig'ilib, qayta ishlangan.

Magistrlik dissertatsiyasining birinchi bobida marketing faoliyatining nazariy asoslari va sport sohasida marketingni qo'llashning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari ko'rib chiqiladi. Ikkinchi qism esa "Shirintoy" bolalar markazi misolida sport sohasida marketing faoliyati amaliyotini tahlil qilish bilan bog'liq. Yakuniy bobda marketing faoliyatini takomillashtirish bo'yicha ishlab chiqilgan tavsiyalar keltirilgan.

REFERENCES

1. Балтаева И. Т. и др. USE OF VIRTUAL LABORATORIES TO CONDUCT FOOTBALL TRAINING //MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 709-718.
2. Jumayev U. X., Kazoqov R. T., Abdusalomov I. K. QUANTITATIVE EVALUATION OF QUALITY INDICATORS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 229-240.
3. Qutlimurotov I. X. et al. THE PROCESS OF ORGANIZING EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES OF STUDENTS AND MASTERING PERSONAL PROFESSIONAL KNOWLEDGE //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 869-879.
4. Солиев И. Р. и др. МОРФО-ФУНКЦИОНАЛ ВА АНТРОПОГЕНЕТИК ТАДҚИҚОТ НАТИЖАЛАРГА КЎРА ФУТБОЛЧИЛАРНИНГ ИШЧАНЛИК НАТИЖАЛАРИНИ БАШОРАТ ҚИЛИШ //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6.
5. Тажибаев С. С. и др. ЖАХОН ЧЕМПИОНАТИ 2022 ЙИЛГИ ФУТБОЛЧИЛАР АНТРОПОМЕТРИК ЎЛЧАМЛАРИ ВА ТЕЗЛИК СИФАТИ ОРАСИДАГИ КОРРЕЛЯЦИЯНИ ЎРГАНИШ //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6.
6. Тажибаев С. С. и др. 13-14 ЁШЛИ ФУТБОЛЧИЛАРНИНГ ТЕХНИК-ТАКТИК ҲАРАКАТЛАРИНИ ТАРБИЯЛАШ САМАРАДОРЛИГИ //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6.
7. Boltayeva I. T. et al. PERIODS OF PRODUCTION EDUCATION. THE PERIOD OF INITIATION, PREPARATION, ACQUISITION AND COMPLETION OF THE PROFESSION //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 561-569.
8. Ganieva M. et al. THE UNITY OF TECHNIQUE, TACTICS AND STRATEGY IN TABLE TENNIS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 1175-1183.
9. Usmonova S. H., Akmurodov M., Kazokov R. THE INFLUENCE OF TEMPERAMENT ON THE CHOICE OF SPORTS ACTIVITIES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 63-70.
10. Umaraliyeva F. T., Kazoqov R. T. THE ROLE OF SPORTSWOMEN IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY AND IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SPORTS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 1124-1131.
11. Mustafayeva N. A., Kazoqov R. T. USING THE MAIN CHARACTERISTICS AND POSSIBILITIES OF THE ELECTRONIC SCHEDULE IN SOLVING ISSUES RELATED TO PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 1115-1123.

- 12.Kazoqov R. T., Axatov L. K. SPORT TOMOSHASINING ESTETIKASI. – 2024.
- 13.Jumayev U. X. et al. " PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION INNOVATION CLUSTER" MEANS COMMON GOALS AND SPECIFIC INTERESTS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 552-560.
- 14.Umarov D. X. et al. NATIONAL MOVEMENT FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS'PHYSICAL PREPARATION USING GAMES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 732-741.
- 15.Umarov D. X. et al. THE EFFECTIVENESS OF USING A SET OF SPECIAL EXERCISES IN ANNUAL PREPARATION TRAINING OF SHORT-DISTANCE RUNNERS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 742-753.
- 16.Jumayev U. X. et al. " PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION INNOVATION CLUSTER" MEANS COMMON GOALS AND SPECIFIC INTERESTS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 552-560.
- 17.Turopovich K. R., Rixsibayevna D. S. ENHANCING ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING THROUGH PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES. – 2024.
- 18.Kazakov R. T. et al. MULTIMEDIA SYSTEMS AND DISTANCE LEARNING TECHNIQUES IN SPORTS SOX //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 9. – С. 99-105.
- 19.Казоқов Р. Т. и др. МАМЛАКАТИМИЗ ЯНАДА ЮКСАЛИШИДА БОЛАЛАР СПОРТИНИНГ ЎРНИ //Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 9. – С. 5-11.
- 20.Казоқов Р. Т. и др. ПЕДАГОГИКА ОЛИЙ ТАЪЛИМДА КЕЙС-СТАДИ ТАЪЛИМ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯСИ АСОСИДА ПЕДАГОГИК МАҲОРАТИНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ ЮЗАСИДАН ТАЖРИБА-СИНОВ ИШЛАРИНИНГ НАТИЖАЛАРИ //Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 6. – С. 111-115.
- 21.Казоқов Р. Т. Кейс стади технологияларидан фойдаланиб талабаларнинг масофавий таълим технологиялари асосида педагогик маҳоратини шакллантириш //Замонавий футболни ривожлантириш тенденциялари: муаммо ва ечимлари. – Т. 11. – №. 1.
- 22.Jumayev U. X. et al. " PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION INNOVATION CLUSTER" MEANS COMMON GOALS AND SPECIFIC INTERESTS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 552-560.
- 23.Murod o'g'li P. D. MAMLAKATIMIZDA JISMONIY TARBIYA VA SPORTNING RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI. – 2023.
- 24.Achilov O. H. TO INCREASE THE INTEREST OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN SPORTS AND TO MAKE THEM REGULARLY ENGAGE IN SPORTS //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 218-220.
- 25.O'G'Li S. O. S., Nurullayev A. Q. THE ORIGIN AND DEVELOPMENT OF ATHLETICS //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 3. – С. 10-15.
- 26.O'Imasbek S. MIDDLE LONG DISTANCE RUNNING //BOSHQARUV VA ETIKA QOIDALARI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 3. – С. 10-12.

27. Nurullayev A. Q., Ogli S. U. S. JUDO ACHIEVEMENT AT THE 2021 SPORTS COMPETITION AT THE UNIVERSITY //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 10. – №. 2. – С. 234-236.
28. Umarov D. X. et al. THE EFFECTIVENESS OF USING A SET OF SPECIAL EXERCISES IN ANNUAL PREPARATION TRAINING OF SHORT-DISTANCE RUNNERS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 742-753.
29. Jumayev U. X. et al. " PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION INNOVATION CLUSTER" MEANS COMMON GOALS AND SPECIFIC INTERESTS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 552-560.
30. Boltayeva I. T., Tashnazarov D. Y., Kazaqov R. T. TECHNICAL-TACTICS OF 13-14-YEAR-OLD FOOTBALL PLAYERS EFFICIENCY OF EDUCATIONAL ACTIONS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 91-98.
31. Сафаров Ў. К ВОПРОСАМ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ КАЧЕСТВА ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ ВУЗОВ НА ОСНОВЕ СИСТЕМНОГО АНАЛИЗА И СТРАТЕГИЧЕСКОГО МЕНЕДЖМЕНТА //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6.
32. Сафаров Ў. МАМЛАКАТИМИЗДА ЖИСМОНИЙ ТАРБИЯ ВА СПОРТ СОҲАСИДА ДАВЛАТ-ХУСУСИЙ ШЕРИКЛИК АСОСЛАРИ //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6.
33. Сафаров Ў. СПОРТ СОҲАСИДА САМАРАЛИ БОШҚАРИШ ТИЗИМИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6.
34. Сафаров Ў. РОЛЬ СПОРТИВНОГО МЕНЕДЖМЕНТА В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ СПОРТИВНОЙ ИНДУСТРИИ УЗБЕКСКОЙ РЕСПУБЛИКИ //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6.
35. Safarov O. O 'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA SPORT MARKETINGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH YO 'LLARI //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6.
37. Murod o'g'li P. D. МАМЛАКАТИМИЗДА ЖИСМОНИЙ ТАРБИЯ ВА СПОРТИВНИЙ РИВОЖЛАНИШ ИСТИҚБОЛЛАРИ. – 2023.
38. Jumayev U. X. et al. " PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION INNOVATION CLUSTER" MEANS COMMON GOALS AND SPECIFIC INTERESTS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 552-560.
39. Boltayeva I. T., Tashnazarov D. Y., Kazaqov R. T. TECHNICAL-TACTICS OF 13-14-YEAR-OLD FOOTBALL PLAYERS EFFICIENCY OF EDUCATIONAL ACTIONS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 91-98.
40. Boltayeva I. T. et al. ANATOMY OF THE EXACT AND NATURAL SCIENCES TEST TASK //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 99-105.
41. Казоқов Р. Т. и др. ТАЪЛИМ МУАССАСАЛАРИДА ТАРБИЯВИЙ ТАДБИРЛАРДА МИЛЛИЙ-МАЪНАВИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШ. – 2024.
42. Djurayeva X. X., Hodjiyev R. M., Kazaqov R. T. DIFFICULTIES IN TEACHING RUSSIAN AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 316-326.

43. Beknazarov S. H. Q., Kazonov R. T. IDEOLOGICAL THREATS AND IMPORTANT PROBLEMS OF IDEOLOGICAL EDUCATION, NATIONAL HISTORICAL THINKING //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 1016-1029.
44. Boltayeva I. T. et al. ANATOMY OF THE EXACT AND NATURAL SCIENCES TEST TASK //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 99-105.
45. Бойқобилов А. П. и др. ТУРЛИ МАЛАКАЛИ СПОРТЧИЛАР ТОМОНИДАН ЯДРО УЛОҚТИРИШНИНГ НАЗАРИЙ ТАҲЛИЛЛАРИ //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 30-40.
46. Авезова Г. С., Казоқов Р. Т. ҚИСҚА МАСОФАГА ЮГУРУВЧИЛАРНИ МАШҒУЛОТ ЖАРАЁНИДА ҚЎЛЛАНИЛГАН ТИКЛОВЧИ ВОСИТАЛАРНИ ЖИСМОНИЙ ТАЙЁРГАРЛИГИГА ТАЪСИРИ //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 205-214.
47. Шопулатов А. Н., Казоқов Р. Т., Хайдарова Г. М. ҚИСҚА МАСОФАГА ЮГУРУВЧИЛАРНИ ЖИСМОНИЙ ТАЙЁРГАРЛИГИНИ БАҲОЛАШ //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 197-204.
48. Бойқобилов А. П. и др. ТУРЛИ МАЛАКАЛИ СПОРТЧИЛАР ТОМОНИДАН ЯДРО УЛОҚТИРИШНИНГ НАЗАРИЙ ТАҲЛИЛЛАРИ //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 30-40.
49. Yugay L. P. et al. RECOVERY OF THE BODY OF SHORT-DISTANCE RUNNING ATHLETES DURING SPORTS TRAINING //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 365-371.
50. Akbarov A. et al. ANTHROPOMETRIC-PHYSIOLOGICAL INDICATORS OF MIDDLE-DISTANCE RUNNERS AND RECOVERY OF THEIR BODY DURING TRAINING //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 358-364.
51. Kim D. et al. PEDAGOGICAL ANALYSIS OF THE PARTICIPATION OF STUDENT ATHLETES IN THE SWEDISH TEAM AND THE SWEDISH TEAM IN THE UZBEKISTAN CHAMPIONSHIP IN HEIGHT ATHLETICS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 346-353.
52. Nurullayeva D. S. et al. ETHICAL PROBLEMS AND THEM IN THE FIELD OF NATURE SOLUTIONS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 480-486.
53. Kazonov R. T., Djo'rabayev A. M. MEANS OF RECOVERY OF WORKING CAPACITY OF SHORT-DISTANCE RUNNERS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 902-911.
54. Kazonov R. T., Djo'rabayev A. M. DEVELOPMENT OF CYBER SPORTS IN UZBEKISTAN //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 893-901.
55. Yaqubov F. M. et al. METHODOLOGY OF SELECTION OF 10-12-YEAR-OLD PLAYERS AND ORGANIZATION OF TRAINING //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 1271-1279.
56. Казоқов Р. Т. ҚИСҚА МАСОФАГА ЮГУРУВЧИЛАРНИНГ ЖИСМОНИЙ ВА МАХСУС ЖИСМОНИЙ ТАЙЁРГАРЛИК КЎРСАТКИЧЛАРИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ //Fan-Sportga. – 2022. – №. 7. – С. 53-55.

57. Гонашвили А. С. и др. Активный досуг узбекской молодежи в аспекте социологического анализа // Теория и практика физической культуры. – 2020. – №. 3. – С. 8-8.
58. Baltayeva I. T. et al. USE OF VIRTUAL LABORATORIES TO CONDUCT FOOTBALL TRAINING // Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 709-718.
59. Baltayeva I. T. et al. CREATING AN INFORMATION-EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT USING MODERN INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES // Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 700-708.
60. Melziddinov R. A., Akramov B. N., Kazoqov R. T. THE RELATIONSHIP OF THE EFFICIENCY OF TECHNICAL-TACTICAL ACTIONS OF FOOTBALL PLAYERS WITH THE LEVEL OF PHYSICAL PREPARATION // Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 1153-165.
61. Umarov D. X. et al. NATIONAL MOVEMENT FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS' PHYSICAL PREPARATION USING GAMES // Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 732-741.
62. Umarov D. X. et al. THE EFFECTIVENESS OF USING A SET OF SPECIAL EXERCISES IN ANNUAL PREPARATION TRAINING OF SHORT-DISTANCE RUNNERS // Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 742-753.
63. Шопулатов А. Н. Бўлажак мураббийларда жисмоний тарбия ва спорт асосида маънавий қадриятларни ривожлантириш йўллари // Фан-Спортга. – 2019. – №. 1. – С. 67-72.
64. Boltayeva I. T., Tashnazarov D. Y., Kazaqov R. T. TECHNICAL-TACTICS OF 13-14-YEAR-OLD FOOTBALL PLAYERS EFFICIENCY OF EDUCATIONAL ACTIONS // Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 91-98.
65. Boltayeva I. T. et al. ANATOMY OF THE EXACT AND NATURAL SCIENCES TEST TASK // Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 99-105.
66. Казоқов Р. Т. и др. ТАЪЛИМ МУАССАСАЛАРИДА ТАРБИЯВИЙ ТАДБИРЛАРДА МИЛЛИЙ-МАЪНАВИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШ. – 2024.
67. Юсупова Н. Р. Хоноқоқлар тарихи ва таснифи // Academic research in educational sciences. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 1062-1072.
68. Yusupova N. R. NATIONAL-CULTURAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS DEVELOPMENT IN CENTRAL ASIA // Mental Enlightenment Scientific-Methodological Journal. – 2024. – Т. 5. – №. 03. – С. 245-254.
69. Юсупова Н. Р. ОСВЕЩЕНИЕ ВОПРОСОВ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ ЗАЩИТЫ В ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЯХ АЛИШЕРА НАВОИ // Academic research in educational sciences. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 547-553.
70. Юсупова Н. Р. ЖИСМОНИЙ ТАРБИЯ ВА СПОРТ СОҲАСИ РИВОЖЛАНИШИ ХУСУСИДАГИ ФАЛСАФИЙ ФИКРЛАРГА ТАРИХИ // Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 281-285.